
REVIEW: AN AMDO TIBETAN WOMAN'S DAILY LIFE

Reviewed by Gengqiugelai 更求格来 (Konchok Gelek,
Dkon mchog dge legs དཀོན་མཚོག་དགེ་ལེགས།)*

Klu thar rgyal (director, producer).
2021. *An Amdo Tibetan Woman's
Daily Life*. 36.55 mins.
<https://bit.ly/31rxoWq>, Tibetan,
English subtitles. Color.

Klu thar rgyal filmed *An Amdo Tibetan Woman's Daily Life* at his family home in Tsha nag (Chanaihai) Community, Mtsho lho (Hainan) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China using an iPhone 11 Pro. This is a valuable addition to his expanding oeuvre focused on his home area, including the past's everyday (Klu thar rgyal et al. 2021) and present (Klu thar rgyal 2017, Ku thar rgyal 2021).¹

The film follows Klu thar rgyal's mother, Kun thar skyid (b. 1972), from when she gets up in the morning through her daily activity. These activities include making a fire in the home; chanting and making offerings; preparing *rtsam pa* 'parched barley flour mixed with hot tea, butter, and dry cheese', milk tea, yogurt, bread, and dumplings; feeding three cows with straw; collecting cattle and sheep dung; piling and winnowing dung; skinning a dead lamb; heating a tap so her family and livestock will have water; and using social media to learn written Tibetan in the evening.

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¹ Related work on Amdo includes photographs ('Jam dbyangs skyabs and Klu thar rgyal et al. 2018) and a translation of English to Tibetan of Tuttle (2019).

 INTRODUCTION

The setting is Kun thar skyid's home and immediate environs - the sunny side of a hill in the family's fenced winter pasture at 3,400 meters above sea level. The film starts as Kun thar skyid intones *Rje btsun' phags ma sgrol ma la bstod pa bzhugs so 'Praise to the Twenty-one Taras'*,¹ pulls on an old lambskin robe, makes a fire in a stove using straw and dried cow dung in a room in the family's house where she sleeps, cooks, and eats with her husband and three children.

Daybreak has yet to come.

After washing her face and hands, she goes to the family's shrine room. She offers water to images of Buddha, the tenth PaN chen (1938-1989), local *bla ma* (e.g., LA mo yongs 'dzin rin po che), Bka' 'gyur,² Yum dum pa bcu gnyis,³ 'Phags pa brgyad stong ba 'Astasahastrika Prajna Paramita,⁴ and Sangs rgyas sman bla 'the Medicine Buddha' on a large shelf. She offers a butter lamp, turns a prayer wheel, prostrates seven times, recharges an electric butter lamp, and makes two offerings. One offering is smoldering *rtsam pa*, and the other is smoldering roasted barley grains with juniper and fresh milk tea. Both offerings are for *chos skyong srung ma*⁵

¹ "Tara is a tantric meditation deity whose practice is used by practitioners of the Tibetan branch of Vajrayana Buddhism to develop certain inner qualities and understand outer, inner and secret teachings about compassion and emptiness" <https://bit.ly/3GsyuEn> 13 January 2022.

² A sacred collection of Tibetan Buddhist literature representing the "Word of the Buddha" of some 1,000 works. Most were originally written in Sanskrit and translated after the eighth century. In the thirteenth century, the collection was published in one hundred volumes <https://bit.ly/3qHEunn> 20 January 2022.

³ Believing that this brings good health and fortune, many local families have this twelve-volume work (*Shes rab kyi pha rol tu phyin pa stong phrag brgyad pa*) in their homes.

⁴ The best-known Buddhist work from 100 BCE to 100 CE. See more at <https://bit.ly/2NJKQ2w> 7 April 2021.

⁵ Dam can and Dpal ldan lha mo are protective female deities of the Dge lugs Sect of Tibetan Buddhism.

'protective deities' and Yul lha Deity.¹

Around sunrise, Kun thar skyid goes to the family's cowshed with a plastic bucket, where she finds one cow with a broken tether. It has a calf, so this cow has no milk for Kun thar skyid and her family that day. One of the other cows is pregnant, and the other has a newborn calf. After washing her hands, she milks the new mother, leaving two teats untouched for the calf. Her bucket is now almost full of milk.

Kun thar skyid returns from milking to the room where she made a fire and begins heating the milk in a large pot. Her husband and daughter have just gotten up, so she prepares a breakfast of *rtsam pa*, milk tea, and fried bread. She chats with her husband while having breakfast, periodically adding sheep dung to the fire in the stove. Her husband talks about his plan to visit a local older woman and other families, and she is supportive as long as he doesn't drink. After the milk boils, she mixes it with some previous yogurt in a wooden bucket, wraps the bucket with a thick cloth to hold the temperature so it is warm enough to make the yogurt, and places the bucket in the corner of the room so no one will accidentally knock it over.

Kun thar skyid makes bread dough in the morning, puts it in an aluminum pot in the afternoon, and covers it with smoldering hot sheep-dung ash near the house in a hole that is deep enough so it is unlikely nearby grass will catch fire. She worries she might accidentally fall into the hole.

Kun thar skyid's husband comes out of the house after breakfast, carries three straw bales near the house, and scatters them on the ground. After pouring oat seed in metal troughs for sheep in an empty enclosure, he comments that his family's sheep are some of the best local sheep. The sheep race out and feed on the oat seed as he opens the door of the sheep enclosure. After finishing,

¹ Yul = 'place' 'designated place'; lha = 'deity'. A *yul lha* is understood to be male. Local laymen pray to and worship him, beseeching help in matters related to herding, farming, traveling, and wealth (Karmay 2010:250).

they rush to the straw scattered on the ground.

Kun thar skyid goes to the pile of bales near the straw storage room, collects straw in a bag near the bales, carries it to the cow enclosure, and feeds the cows. She separates a cow prone to butting the other cows and sheep and feeds it outside the enclosure.

Kun thar skyid goes a short distance from the house to check a community water source, but when she turns the tap, she realizes it is frozen, so there is no water, which has been the situation for some days. She feels sorry for other locals who will have to get water from another water source that is far away.

Her family has a water tank near the house. The water tank spigot is frozen, so she heats it using smoldering sheep-dung ash. After the spigot thaws, water flows to troughs near the water tank to water the sheep.

Kun thar skyid struggles to skin a half-frozen dead lamb and comments that it probably died from eating wool. She throws the carcass to the family watchdog, sticks the skin on a wall to dry to prevent the family's cat from eating it, and describes making skins into robes.

Kun thar skyid puts cow dung in a bag and carries it on her back to a dung pile near the cow enclosure. After using a big broom to collect sheep dung pellets in the sheep enclosure, she puts them in a bag, carries it to a pile of dung, and winnows the pellets, commenting that this requires about two hours. She adds that in the past, lambs froze if she didn't collect sheep dung regularly from the enclosure. Though this is no longer a threat, thanks to a good sheep enclosure, she explains that collecting dung is necessary for cooking and heating fuel.

At sunset, Kun thar skyid makes dumplings on the *hu tse* 'adobe sleeping-seating platform' near the stove. Her daughter joins her. As Kun thar skyid washes utensils and cleans the room, her oldest son teaches his sister Chinese sign language.

Kun thar skyid checks her phone and comments in amazement at someone making a beautiful *zhun* 'Tibetan cake' on social media. After finishing home chores, she rests on the family's

hu tse, holding a phone in one hand and a pocketbook in the other. She listens to WeChat and explains that a local teacher daily teaches one page from the pocketbook (*Bde smon dang bzang spyod smon lam* 'Book of Collected Prayers'). She repeats what she hears and reads to her teacher what she has learned that day via WeChat. The film ends.

An Amdo Tibetan Woman's Daily Life is not alone in visually documenting ethnographic detail of the lives of female Tibetans. Lynn True et al. (2010) *Summer Pasture* created in a herding area in Rdza chu kha (Shiqu) County, Dkar mdzes (Ganzi) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan Province; and Jamyang ['Jam dbyangs] (2021) made *One Wife and Her Three Husbands* shot in a farming area in Sa skya (Sajia) County, Gzhis ka rtse (Rikaze) City, Tibet Autonomous Region. Both films include the tasks Tibetan wives and husbands assume to ensure the household runs smoothly.

Puhudangzhi (2006) *Tibetan Woman's Daily Life*, Gu ru 'phrin las (2020)¹ *A Tibetan Herdswoman*, and Jamyang ['Jam dbyangs] (2021) *Himalayan Hard-Living Woman* concentrate on a day in a Tibetan housewife's life. Puhudangzhi shot the film in a farming area in Xunhua Salar [Sala] Autonomous County, Mtsho shar (Haidong) City, Mtsho sngon Province. The main character is mainly involved with housework, fieldwork, feeding livestock (swine, a cow, a mule), and collecting wood for fuel. Gu ru 'phrin las' film focuses on a yak herding area in Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log (Guoluo) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Mtsho sngon Province. The main character is an adult woman who milks yaks, collects yak dung for fuel, and collects caterpillar fungus. Jamyang's *Himalayan Hard-Living Woman*, filmed in an agricultural area² in the Tibet Autonomous Region, features milking yaks, making yogurt, and weeding in fields.

Anonymous (2018) filmed collecting yak dung and making stoves from mud in winter by two Tibetan herdswomen (no detailed

¹ This is an abbreviated version of his longer film, *Jeopardy*.

² Specific location is not given.

location given).

Chaud (2007) and Deutsche Stiftung für Internationale Entwicklung (2008) were shot in villages in Zanskar (Ladakh) and highlighted women harvesting crops and two adolescent sisters' life choices, respectively.¹

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Kun thar skyid's daily mundane chores from dawn to dusk portray real life without a hint of artificial performance, made possible by her relationship with the cameraman, her son. The lack of a recorded soundtrack emphasizes this lack of artificiality. Instead, the bleating of sheep; a dog barking; noises of Kun thar skyid's movements; sounds made by fire, water, and wind; and the family's non-performative conversation position these images in an authentic framework of Tibetan winter days.

Certain aspects of this film deserve further attention. When Kun thar skyid has a moment of her own, she studies how to read Tibetan through social media networks, demonstrating the spontaneous, grassroots-level eliminate-illiteracy movement. Kun thar skyid has qualities many rural Tibetan women share. She is hardworking, spiritual, dutiful, and caring. In combination, these characteristics create the backbone of a household and society at large. Kun thar skyid's wrinkled face and downturned eyes further express her life in a perpetual cycle of chores with no end in sight.

Although the family's living circumstances have changed from mobile pastoralism to a settled life with electricity and more convenient access to water, life continues to change. Kun thar skyid may be the last generation of traditional housewives wearing heavy, inconvenient robes while working. The impact of education and the opportunities it provides substantially differentiate her children from her generation. For example, Kun thar skyid's rough overworked hands are in sharp contrast to her daughter's pale

¹ Feature films by Pad ma tshe brtan (e.g., *Tharlo*, *Balloon*, *Jinpa*) and Zon thar rgyal (e.g., *River*) have made feature films with hired performers in key roles. See Khashem Gyal (2017), Phun tshogs dbang rgyal (2017), and Robin (2020) for more.

hands with polished blueish nails, whose fashionable appearance further suggests she has opted for a lifestyle very different from that of her mother's generation.

In little more than thirty-six minutes, this film accomplishes a great deal by intimately portraying an unromanticized day in Kun thar skyid's winter life and, more broadly, the lives of rural Tibetan women in 2021 and sheep raising in Mtsho lho.

Kun thar skyid speaking directly to the camera is particularly valuable.

This pastoralist community will continue to evolve, emphasizing this film's relevance and value to Tibetologists, Mtsho sngon specialists, and students of Himalayan communities, and as a chronicle of Tibetan rural life in transition in the early 2020s. Given the ubiquity of mobile phones and their constantly improving camera features, this film challenges young people across the Tibetosphere to produce video/audio records of home life.

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TIBETAN TERMS

'brog pa འབྲོག་པ།	klu thar rgyal ལྷ་ཐར་རྒྱལ།
'jam dbyangs འཇམ་དབྱངས།	kun thar skyid ལུན་ཐར་སྐྱིད།
'phags pa brgyad stong ba འཕགས་པ་བརྒྱད་སྟོང་བ།	la mo yongs 'dzin rin po che ལཱ་མོ་ཡོངས་འཛིན་རིན་པོ་ཅེ།
'phags pa don grub འཕགས་པ་དོན་གྲུབ།	lha mo mtsho ལྷ་མོ་མཚོ།
amdo, a mdo མ་མདོ།	mgo log མགོ་ལོག།
bde smon dang bzang spyod smön lam བདེ་སྐྱོན་དང་བཟང་སྟོད་སྐྱོན་ལམ།	mgo mang མགོ་མང།
bla ma ལྷ་མ།	mkha' byams rgyal མཁའ་བྱམས་རྒྱལ།
bka' 'gyur བཀའ་འགྲུབ།	mtsho lho མཚོ་ལྷོ།
chos skyong srung ma ཚོས་སྐྱོང་སྲུང་མ།	mtsho shar མཚོ་ཤར།
dam can དམ་ཅན།	mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྟོན།
dge lugs དགེ་ལུགས།	paN chen པཎ་ཅེན།
dkar mdzes དཀར་མཛེས།	pad ma tshe brtan པད་མ་ཅེ་བརྟན།
dpal ldan lha mo དཔལ་ལྷན་ལྷ་མོ།	phun tshogs dbang rgyal ཕུན་ཚོགས་དབང་རྒྱལ།
dpal rgyal དཔལ་རྒྱལ།	rdo rje རོ་རྗེ།
gcig sgril གཅིག་སྐྱིལ།	rdza chu kha རྩ་ཅུ་ཀམ།
gu ru 'phrin las གུ་རུ་འཕྲིན་ལས།	rin chen རིན་ཅེན།
gzhis ka rtse གཞིས་ཀ་རེ།	rje btsun 'phags ma sgröl ma ལཱ་མོ་པོད་པ་བཞུགས་སོ་
hu tse ལུ་ཅེ།	འཕགས་མ་སྐྱོལ་མ་ལ་བརྟོད་པ་བཞུགས་སོ།
	rtsam pa རྩམ་པ།

sa skya ས་སྐྱལ།
 sangs rgyas sman bla སངས་རྒྱལ་སྐལ་བུ་བླ་མ་
 ལྷ།
 sgrol ma སྐྱོལ་མ།
 shes rab kyi pha rol tu phyin
 pa stong phrag brgyad pa
 ཤེས་རབ་ཀྱི་པ་རོལ་ཏུ་ཕྱིན་པ་ལྟོང་ཕྱག་བརྒྱད་པ།

thar lo ཐར་ལོ།
 tsha nag ཚ་ནག།
 yul lha ཡུལ་ལྷ།
 yum dum pa bcu gnyis
 ཡུམ་དུམ་པ་བརྒྱ་གཉིས།
 zhun ལུན།
 zon thar rgyal རྩོན་ཐར་རྒྱལ།

CHINESE TERMS

Chanaihai 查乃亥
 Gengqiugelai 更求格来
 Guoluo 果洛
 Haidong 海东
 Ganzi 甘孜
 Hainan 海南
 Jiuzhi 久治

Puhudangzhi 普华当智
 Qinghai 青海
 Rikaze 日喀则
 Sajia 萨迦
 Sala 撒拉
 Shiqu 石渠
 Xunhua 循化